

As on 01-04-2020, the following data entry procedures are recommended in order to make a record of Focus Crop into the knowledge base system. Focus crops are selected based on the research interest in Crops For the Future Research Centre. The list of focus crops is to help our data collection efforts to be more focused.

Steps for data entry:

1. This table is the record of Crop For the Future's possible next focused crops. All the crops listed on this table are underutilised crops of annual grains (cereals, pseudo-cereals), annual vegetables (leafy, tuber, fruity) and perennial fruit. There are two fields to be entered:

1.1 Crop (compulsory)

- This is referring to the common name of Focus Crop.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name in the 'Crop' field.

1.2 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the crop itself.